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Neurophysiological Basis of Balance Dysfunction in Multiple Sclerosis: Neuroanatomical Insights and Central Mechanisms

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70 **Neurophysiological Basis of Balance Dysfunction in Multiple** 71 **Sclerosis: Neuroanatomical Insights and Central Mechanisms** 72

73 **Abstract:**

74 Balance dysfunction is a cardinal early symptom in patients with multiple sclerosis (PwMS).
75 Despite its clinical importance, the neuropathophysiological mechanisms underlying this dys-
76 function remain unclear. Developing specific and effective interventions that address this prob-
77 lem requires identification of the neuroanatomical regions involved and understanding the im-
78 pact of their functional impairments on different types of balance control systems. Although a
79 previous review in 2018 identified some of these regions, it did not explore how their corre-
80 sponding functional impairments affect different types of balance control systems, highlighting
81 a significant gap in our understanding of these mechanisms. Therefore, the aim of this review
82 was to provide a detailed and comprehensive synthesis of both previously identified and newly
83 discovered neuroanatomical correlates involved in balance dysfunction in PwMS and examine
84 how functional impairments within these regions influence distinct aspects of balance control,
85 including static and dynamic balance. By conducting such research, this review offers novel
86 insights into the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying balance dysfunction in PwMS and
87 proposes a framework that can aid clinicians in selecting targeted interventions for specific im-
88 pairments. Ultimately, this review has broader clinical implications beyond theoretical
89 knowledge, potentially contributing to enhanced therapeutic outcomes and improved patient
90 care.

91 **Keywords:** postural balance; neural pathways; neuroanatomy; functional impairments, multi-
92 ple sclerosis.

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114 **Bases neurophysiologiques de la dysfonction de l'équilibre dans la**
115 **sclérose en plaques : aperçus neuroanatomiques et mécanismes**
116 **centraux**

117 **Résumé:**

118 La dysfonction de l'équilibre est un symptôme précoce majeur chez les patients atteints de sclé-
119 rose en plaques (SEP). Malgré son importance clinique, les mécanismes neuropathophysiolo-
120 giques sous-jacents restent mal compris. Le développement d'interventions efficaces nécessite
121 l'identification des régions neuroanatomiques impliquées et la compréhension de l'impact de
122 leurs altérations fonctionnelles sur les systèmes de contrôle de l'équilibre. Une revue de 2018 a
123 identifié certaines de ces régions, mais n'a pas examiné comment les altérations fonctionnelles
124 influencent les différents types de contrôle de l'équilibre, mettant ainsi en évidence une lacune
125 importante dans notre compréhension de ces mécanismes.

126 Cette revue vise à synthétiser les corrélats neuroanatomiques, déjà identifiés et récemment dé-
127 couverts, impliqués dans la dysfonction de l'équilibre chez les patients atteints de SEP. Elle
128 explore également comment les altérations fonctionnelles dans ces régions affectent l'équilibre
129 statique et dynamique. En abordant ces mécanismes, cette revue apporte des perspectives nou-
130 velles sur les fondements neurophysiologiques de la dysfonction de l'équilibre et propose un
131 cadre pouvant aider les cliniciens à sélectionner des interventions ciblées en fonction des défi-
132 cits identifiés.

133 En fin de compte, cette revue pourrait avoir des implications cliniques larges, contribuant à de
134 meilleures stratégies thérapeutiques et à une amélioration des soins aux patients.

135 **Mots clés:** Équilibre postural; voies nerveuses; neuroanatomie; déficits fonctionnels, sclérose
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170 **1. Introduction**

171 Balance dysfunction is an early cardinal symptom in patients with multiple sclerosis (PwMS)
172 (Cameron & Lord, 2010; Fling et al., 2014; Prosperini et al., 2013). It is widely recognized as
173 one of the most disabling symptoms (Prosperini et al., 2013, 2014) as it decreases independence
174 and mobility, increases the risk of falls that can lead to injuries or death, and affects the overall
175 quality of life (Mazumder et al., 2014; Prosperini et al., 2014). Notably, it does not only affect
176 patients with significant disability and advanced disease (Capone et al., 2019), but is also prev-
177 alent in patients who demonstrate minimal or no clinical manifestations (Capone et al., 2019;
178 Fling et al., 2014; Martin et al., 2006). As the disease progresses, this problem becomes more
179 pronounced (Fling et al., 2014).

180 Despite its clinical importance, the specific pathophysiological mechanisms underlying balance
181 dysfunction in PwMS remained unclear (Capone et al., 2019; Peterson et al., 2016; Prosperini
182 et al., 2013, 2014). Consequently, researchers have attempted to investigate the neural correlates
183 underlying this dysfunction. Initially, these findings were primarily attributed to spinal cord
184 lesions, excluding the potential involvement of the cerebellum (Cameron et al., 2008). How-
185 ever, subsequent evidence has increasingly highlighted the detrimental influence of cerebellar
186 lesions on balance control, suggesting a more complex mechanism underlying balance dysfunc-
187 tion. As research has advanced, it has become evident that balance impairments among PwMS
188 cannot be attributed to a single neural structure. Instead, more recent findings suggest that it is
189 multifactorial, varying among patients due to widespread and variable damage to the central
190 nervous system (CNS) (Cameron et al., 2008; Prosperini et al., 2013, 2014).

191 These evolving findings on the neural correlates underlying balance dysfunction in PwMS un-
192 derscore the complexity of its mechanisms and highlight the importance of identifying the in-
193 volved neuroanatomical regions. A comprehensive understanding of how functional impair-
194 ments within these regions affect different aspects of balance control is crucial for developing
195 targeted and effective interventions (Fling et al., 2014). Given that balance is increasingly rec-
196 ognized as a task-specific motor skill rather than a general (Ibrahim et al., 2024; Cattaneo et al.,
197 2014; Conner et al., 2019; Dunskey, Zeev, & Netz, 2017; Hrysomallis, McLaughlin & Goodman,
198 2006; Karimi & Solomonidis, 2011; Kiss, Schedler & Muehlbauer, 2018; Muehlbauer et al.,
199 2012; Paillard et al., 2004; Pau et al., 2017; Shimada et al., 2003; Tsigilis, Zachopoulou &
200 Mavridis, 2001) and interventions that are effective in addressing specific impairments may not
201 necessarily be effective in addressing others (Blasco et al., 2023; Cattaneo et al., 2014; Dunskey,
202 Zeev, & Netz, 2017; Hrysomallis, McLaughlin & Goodman, 2006; Paillard et al., 2004), it is
203 imperative to tailor interventions accordingly. Therefore, deeper insight into the physiological
204 mechanisms underlying balance dysfunction is essential for the development of targeted reha-
205 bilitation strategies that optimize therapeutic outcomes.

206 In this context, a prior review conducted in 2018 (Prosperini & Castelli, 2018) identified several
207 neuroanatomical regions implicated in balance dysfunction in PwMS. Although this review
208 provided valuable insights, it did not explore how functional impairments within these regions
209 affect various aspects of balance control systems. As a result, significant gaps remain in our
210 understanding of the underlying mechanisms that contribute to balance dysfunction in PwMS.
211 Therefore, the aim of this review is 1- to provide a detailed and comprehensive synthesis of
212 both previously identified and newly discovered neuroanatomical correlates involved in balance
213 dysfunction in PwMS and 2- to examine how functional impairments within these regions in-
214 fluence distinct aspects of balance control, including static and dynamic balance, across varying

215 sensory conditions. By systematically analyzing these relationships, this review aims to address
216 the existing gap in literature, which is crucial for advancing both theoretical knowledge and
217 clinical practice.

218 To achieve the study objectives, we will conduct a thorough review of the literature and identi-
219 fying studies that investigate the correlations between lesions to specific neural structures with
220 balance measures in PwMS. Additionally, we will explore how lesions in these regions contrib-
221 ute to distinct balance control deficits and the resulting impairments arising from such lesions.
222 By integrating these multidimensional perspectives, this review aims to offer novel insights into
223 the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying balance dysfunction in PwMS. To the best of
224 our knowledge, this is the first comprehensive synthesis of this kind, providing advanced in-
225 sights that broaden our understanding of this issue and offer clinicians a critical foundation for
226 developing targeted therapeutic interventions. Ultimately, this can enhance therapeutic out-
227 comes, reduce the risk of falls, and significantly improve the quality of life of PwMS.

228 In subsequent sections, we provide a structured and detailed presentation of our methodology,
229 results, and discussion. Specifically, in the “Materials and Methods” section, we comprehen-
230 sively describe the methodological approach employed in this review, including the databases
231 searched, criteria for study inclusion and exclusion, and process used to identify relevant stud-
232 ies. In the “Results” section, we present a thorough analysis of the neural structures implicated
233 in balance dysfunction, the impact of lesions within these structures on various aspects of bal-
234 ance control, and the specific balance impairments resulting from these lesions. Finally, in the
235 “Discussion” section, we synthesize the key findings of this review, interpret their implications
236 in the context of the existing literature, and offer clinically relevant recommendations for as-
237 sessing and treating balance impairments in PwMS.

238 **2. Materials and Methods**

239 The required data was obtained by reviewing previous studies that aimed to establish correla-
240 tions between neuroimaging (i.e., magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)), and/or neurophysiolog-
241 ical test findings (i.e., somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEP)) of different regions of the CNS
242 with balance measures (i.e., force platform and balance scales) in PwMS.

243 This review was conducted by searching for relevant studies in PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google
244 Scholar, and Research Gate. The inclusion criteria were as follows: 1) articles that aimed to
245 investigate the correlation between the involvement of different CNS regions and both postural
246 and balance dysfunction in PwMS; 2) studies that utilized subjective tools, such as stabilometer,
247 and objective tools, such as scales to evaluate postural and balance dysfunction; and 3) studies
248 that utilized objective tools only to assess the involvement of CNS regions, such as MRI and
249 SSEP. The exclusion criteria were as follows: 1) studies that examined correlations between the
250 involvement of different CNS regions and balance dysfunction in other disorders, including
251 clinically isolated syndrome; 2) studies that utilized standardized clinical scales, such as the
252 Functional System Score (FSS), to evaluate functional impairments in specific neural systems,
253 including the pyramidal, cerebellar, and brainstem systems, thereby indirectly inferring their
254 involvement; 3) studies that investigated the correlation between the involvement of different
255 CNS regions and general disability without specifically addressing balance impairments as an
256 independent measure; and 4) studies that were only available as abstract papers without full-
257 text articles.

258 A total of 1675 studies were initially identified. After removing duplicates ($n = 40$), 1635 studies
259 were screened based on their titles and abstracts. Among these, 1487 studies were excluded
260 based on their titles, and an additional 128 studies were excluded based on their abstracts. Of
261 these 128 studies, 47 were excluded because they focused on the association between CNS

262 imaging with disability, 32 for evaluating changes in different CNS regions in PwMS using
263 imaging techniques, 9 for evaluating the potential of developing new imaging techniques for
264 diagnosing MS, 8 for correlating CNS imaging findings with other impairments (i.e., gait im-
265 pairments, strength, cognition), 5 for correlating posturography measures and other impair-
266 ments (i.e., strength, disability, fatigue, spasticity), 4 for evaluating the contribution of sensory
267 problems (i.e., vision and proprioception) to balance using posturography, 3 for correlating
268 posturography measures with the risk of falls, 3 for evaluating the potential of posturography
269 in detecting balance problems when clinical tests are un able or in the absence of other clinical
270 manifestations in early MS stages, and 17 for other less frequent reasons. Subsequently, 20
271 papers were screened for eligibility, and ultimately, 18 papers were included after excluding
272 one paper due to quality concerns and one paper due to the absence of full text availability
273 (Figure 1).

274 **3. Results**

275 ***3.1. Spinal Cord Involvement (Involvement of the Dorsal Column Medial Lemniscus*** 276 ***Pathway and Other Spinal Tracts)***

277 The spinal cord is an integral component of the CNS (Khan & Lui, 2024; Nógrádi & Vrbová,
278 2013), located within the vertebral canal (Khan & Lui, 2024; Peabody, Black & Das, 2024). It
279 has a well-organized cylindrical shape (Ganapathy, Reddy & Tadi, 2024), structured into dis-
280 tinct ascending and descending tracts, each with a specific function (Harrow-Mortelliti, Reddy
281 & Jimsheleishvili, 2024). The ascending tracts transmit sensory inputs from receptors to higher
282 levels of the CNS. While, the descending tracts carry inputs from higher levels of the CNS to
283 the periphery (Harrow-Mortelliti, Reddy & Jimsheleishvili, 2024).

284 One of the ascending tracts of the spinal cord is the dorsal column medial lemniscus pathway
285 (DCML) (Harrow-Mortelliti, Reddy & Jimsheleishvili, 2024), also known as the dorsal column

286 (Al-Chalabi., Reddy, & Als Salman, 2022). This pathway is responsible for transmitting cutane-
287 ous and proprioceptive information from the periphery to the primary somatosensory cortex
288 (S1). The ipsilateral posterior columns carry signals from joint and cutaneous receptors, mus-
289 cular branches, and spindle Ia and II afferents to the nucleus cuneatus and gracilis of the medulla
290 oblongata. At this level, these signals synapse with the internal arcuate fibers, decussate, and
291 then ascend to the contralateral somatosensory area of the thalamus, through the medial lem-
292 niscus. Afferent information from the muscle spindle reaches the primary somatosensory cortex
293 (S1), specifically the Brodmann area (BA) 3a, through thalamocortical projections, whereas
294 afferent cutaneous information reaches BA 3b (MacKinnon, 2018) (Figure 2) . Studies have
295 demonstrated that spinal cord dysfunction, particularly DCML, delays postural responses
296 (Cameron et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2020), impairs standing balance in both eyes open (Abdel-
297 Aziz et al., 2015; Arpan et al., 2020; Zackowski et al., 2009) and closed conditions (Arpan et
298 al., 2020; Fling et al., 2014), and impairs dynamic balance in PwMS (Capone et al., 2019).

299

300 **3.1.1. *Delayed postural responses following unexpected perturbations:***

301 Spinal cord dysfunction has been recognized as a potential contributing factor to delayed re-
302 sponses in PwMS. (Cameron et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2020). Specifically, studies has found that
303 slowed conduction (Cameron et al., 2008; Huisinga et al., 2014) and structural damage (Lee et
304 al., 2020) to both spinal afferent pathways, specifically DCML, (Cameron et al., 2008; Huisinga
305 et al., 2014) and efferent pathways (Huisinga et al., 2014) can lead to this impairment. The
306 proposed role of the spinal cord in initiating and contributing to postural responses (Deliagina
307 et al., 2014; Jacobs & Horak, 2007) may explain these findings. Consequently, slowed conduc-
308 tion of the spinal somatosensory signals delays proprioceptive feedback, ultimately resulting in
309 incorrect or delayed compensatory postural adjustments (Fling et al., 2014). However, impaired

310 motor pathways and subsequent alterations in muscle tissue secondary to such neural damage
311 disrupt efficient recruitment of motor units and adequate summation (Thigpen et al., 2009). This
312 in turn results in inaccurate motor commands, characterized by a delay in the generation of rapid
313 postural responses and a reduced capacity to generate sufficient torque necessary for maintain-
314 ing or restoring postural stability (Thigpen et al., 2009).

315 **3.1.2. Impaired static standing in eyes open and closed conditions:**

316 Previous studies have further established that spinal cord dysfunction contributes to static bal-
317 ance impairments in PwMS under both eyes open and closed conditions. These impairments
318 are thought to result from damage to the ascending and descending tracts of the spinal cord
319 (Abdel-Aziz et al., 2015; Arpan et al., 2020; Fling et al., 2014).

320 In the ascending tracts: Lesions involving the dorsal column have been implicated in balance
321 dysfunction across both visual conditions (Zackowski et al., 2009) (Fling et al., 2014), with
322 particular influence of proprioceptive tracts originating and terminating at Brodmann area 3a
323 (BA 3a) of the right hemisphere on balance performance during eyes closed condition (Fling et
324 al., 2014).

325 Conceptually, the established relationship between DCML pathways and static balance dys-
326 function can be attributed to the prominent role of the proprioceptive system in controlling
327 standing balance. When standing on a fixed support surface with eyes open, healthy adults
328 weigh the sensory system feedback necessary for balance control as 70% for the proprioceptive
329 system, 20% for the vestibular system, and 10% for the visual system (Bekkers et al., 2014;
330 Fling et al., 2014; Richmond et al., 2021). This sensory weighting emphasizes the predominance
331 of proprioception in balance maintenance under normal conditions. Consequently, the interrup-
332 tion of these inputs increases body sway (Fling et al., 2014) and results in postural instability
333 that is further exacerbated during eyes closed conditions, when reliance on proprioceptive input

334 is heightened (Gera, Fling & Horak, 2020; Prosperini et al., 2014). As a result, lesions affecting
335 the DCML critically impair static balance in PwMS, across both visual conditions by interrupt-
336 ing proprioceptive feedback, reinforcing its central role in maintaining postural stability.

337 In the descending tracts: In contrast to the relatively well-characterized impact of ascending
338 pathways on postural control in PwMS, much less is known about the role of descending tracts.
339 Although lesions in the descending pathways are thought to contribute to balance dysfunction
340 in PwMS, the specific pathways responsible for this dysfunction remain poorly understood.
341 This finding highlights the need for further research to elucidate their impact on balance control.
342 A more detailed understanding of the pathways involved and the impact of their functional
343 impairments on balance, could support the development of targeted rehabilitation strategies
344 aimed at improving balance in PwMS.

345 ***3.1.3. Impaired dynamic balance:***

346 In PwMS, impaired sensory and motor spinal cord pathways contribute to balance impairment,
347 extending beyond static deficits to include dynamic balance dysfunction. These impairments
348 manifest as biomechanical alterations in the gait kinematics and trunk control. Kinematic
349 changes are often characterized by impaired joint movement and reduced power generation,
350 arising from complex and incompletely understood mechanisms, including slowed conduction
351 of spinal somatosensory pathways, leg asymmetry, and impaired sensorimotor integration
352 (Huisinga et al., 2013).

353 Trunk control during gait in PwMS is influenced by postural response latency. Specifically,
354 patients with delayed postural responses exhibit greater trunk motion in the sagittal
355 (anteroposterior, AP) plane, suggesting a compensatory mechanism characterized by increased
356 movement amplitude in response to delayed stabilization. Simultaneously, they exhibit reduced

357 variability in the transverse (mediolateral, ML) plane, suggesting a compensatory stiffening
358 strategy to enhance lateral stability (Huisinga et al., 2014). This strategy, however, is
359 characterized by chaotic and less stable motor control, despite the restricted range of motion
360 (Huisinga et al., 2013). Combined with spasticity, muscle weakness, and fatigue, these altera-
361 tions in trunk movement impair dynamic balance and contribute to increased fall risk in PwMS
362 (Huisinga et al., 2014).

363 ***3.2. Cerebellar Involvement***

364 The cerebellum, or “little brain” in Latin (Unverdi & Alsayouri, 2023), is a key brain structure
365 that is interconnected with major loops in the spinal cord, brainstem, and cerebral cortex
366 (D’Angelo, 2018). It receives and transmits various types of information to and from the cere-
367 bellum through its peduncles, namely the superior, middle, and inferior cerebellar peduncles
368 (CP) (Gera, Fling & Horak, 2020; Ye et al., 2015). The cerebellum is composed of anterior,
369 posterior, and flocculonodular lobes, each of which is further subdivided into lobules (Kim et
370 al., 2020; Amore et al., 2021). Lobules I-V form the anterior lobe, lobules VI-IX form the pos-
371 terior lobe, and lobule X form the flocculonodular lobe (Amore et al., 2021). Studies have
372 shown that cerebellar dysfunction in PwMS impairs standing and dynamic balance control.

373 ***3.2.1. Impaired static standing balance:***

374 Previous research has established a relationship between dysfunction in specific cerebellar re-
375 gions and standing balance impairments in PwMS. Specifically, this relationship has been ob-
376 served in patients with impaired cerebellar somatosensory lobules (lobules I–IV and VIII) and
377 cerebellar peduncles. Studies have shown that atrophy of the cerebellar somatosensory lobules
378 in PwMS leads to standing balance dysfunction, in both eyes open (Prosperini et al., 2013;

379 Ruggieri et al., 2020) and closed (Ruggieri et al., 2020) conditions. In particular, Ruggieri et
380 al., (2020) found that atrophy of lobules I–IV (anterior cerebellum) critically contributes to bal-
381 ance dysfunction in both eyes open and closed conditions, while atrophy of lobule VIIIb
382 strongly correlates with clinical disability, as measured by the Expanded Disability Status Scale
383 (EDSS) and the 25-Foot Walk Test (25-FWT). Multivariate regression identified lobule VIIIb
384 as the strongest independent predictor of disability (EDSS: $\beta = -0.37$, $p < 0.01$; 25-FWT: $\beta =$
385 -0.45 , $p < 0.001$), while lobules I–IV specifically predicted balance impairment (C-EO/C-EC:
386 $\beta = -0.36$ to -0.37 , $p < 0.01$), explaining 16–22% of the variance. Similarly, Prosperini et al.,
387 (2013) found that gray matter atrophy in lobules I–IV–VI and lobule VIII was significantly
388 associated with standing balance impairments, particularly under eyes open conditions. This
389 suggests that lobules I–IV and VIII contribute to balance control via sensorimotor integration.
390 Moreover, lobule VIIIb function critically influences gait and broader disability.

391 In addition to cerebellar lobular atrophy, other studies have highlighted the impact of impaired
392 microstructural integrity of the cerebellar peduncles on balance control in PwMS under various
393 sensory conditions. Specifically, studies have found that impaired microstructural integrity of
394 the superior cerebellar peduncles (SCP) affects static stance on a fixed support surface with the
395 eyes open (Gera, Fling & Horak, 2020). Impaired microstructural integrity of the middle cere-
396 bellar peduncles (MCP) affects visual-based balance control (standing on a compliant support
397 surface with eyes open) (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021). Whereas, impaired microstructural
398 integrity of the inferior cerebellar peduncles (ICP) affects static stance on a fixed support sur-
399 face with eyes open (Gera, Fling & Horak, 2020), proprioceptive-based balance (standing on a
400 fixed support surface with eyes closed), and vestibular-based balance (standing on a compliant
401 support surface with eyes closed) (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021). Conceptually, the impact
402 of lesions in each cerebellar peduncle on balance control under different sensory conditions can

403 be attributed to the specific types of information that each peduncle transmits to the cerebellum.
404 For instance, the MCP transmits visual information to the cerebellum (Gera, Fling & Horak,
405 2020; Ruggieri et al., 2020). Consequently, impairments in its microstructural integrity affect
406 visual-based balance. In contrast, the ICP carries and integrates proprioceptive (Kim, Tak &
407 Son, 2014.; Zampieri et al., 2023) and vestibular information in the cerebellum (Ruggieri et al.,
408 2020). Therefore, impairments in its microstructural integrity affect static stance with the eyes
409 open and closed, as well as vestibular-based balance. These findings highlight the crucial role
410 of the cerebellar peduncles in conveying multisensory information to the cerebellum. Subse-
411 quently, impairments in the microstructural integrity of the cerebellar peduncles affect standing
412 balance control by affecting cerebellar regulation, integration and reweighting processes
413 (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021).

414 ***3.2.2. Impaired dynamic balance:***

415 The detrimental effect of cerebellar dysfunction on balance performance in PwMS extends be-
416 yond impairments in standing balance to include pronounced impairments in dynamic balance
417 control (Eskut et al., 2021). A recent graphical-LASSO network analysis demonstrated by Eskut
418 et al., (2021) provided specific evidence that dynamic balance performance in PwMS, as meas-
419 ured by the Berg Balance Scale (BBS) and Timed 25-Foot Walk Test (25FWT), is linked to
420 distinct cerebellar regions. The BBS score showed a positive partial correlation with bilateral
421 lobule X, suggesting that better balance performance is linked to preserved structural integrity
422 of these lobules. Conversely, the 25FWT demonstrated negative partial correlations with ante-
423 rior cerebellar lobules III and V (right, left, and total), indicating that impaired mobility and
424 slower gait were correlated with reduced integrity of these lobules.

425 Physiologically, the cerebellum is a critical structure within the central nervous system that
426 contributes to postural control through several mechanisms, including feed-forward (Prosperini
427 et al., 2014; Takakusaki, 2017) and feedback mechanisms (Takakusaki, 2017; Yanagihara,
428 2014), as well as sensory integration and reweighting process (Odem, Richmond & Fling,
429 2021). These processes are essential for maintaining postural stability under both static and
430 dynamic conditions (Cattaneo et al., 2007; Rasman et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2023; Takakusaki,
431 2017; Yanagihara, 2014) such as during gait and mobility. Therefore, cerebellar atrophy or focal
432 lesions may disrupt these mechanisms, leading to a compromised balance control in PwMS
433 across a range of postural demands.

434 ***3.3. Brainstem Involvement***

435 The brainstem, a CNS structure (Purves et al., 2001), connects the cerebrum to the cerebellum
436 and spinal cord. It is composed of the midbrain, pons, and medulla oblongata and is widely
437 recognized as a critical site for vital functions, such as respiration (Basinger & Hogg, 2022).
438 The white matter (WM) tracts within the brainstem facilitate the relay and processing of signals
439 between the spinal cord and brain (Gowda & De Jesus, 2022). Studies have shown that brain-
440 stem dysfunction in PwMS impairs standing balance control even on relatively stable surfaces
441 and results in delayed postural responses to external perturbations. This was particularly evident
442 in studies by Prosperini et al. (2011) and Peterson et al. (2016). Specifically, Prosperini et al.,
443 (2011) reported a significant correlation between brainstem T2 lesion volume (T2-LV) with
444 both mediolateral velocity (VEL-ML) and center of pressure (COP) path length during static
445 standing with eyes open ($r = 0.57$, $p = 0.001$ for both). Whereas, Peterson et al., (2016). observed
446 significantly reduced WM tract integrity, measured by radial diffusivity, in the pedunculo-
447 tine nucleus (PPN)-balance/locomotor network of PwMS compared to healthy controls ($p =$

448 0.004), which was strongly correlated with delayed muscle activation in response to perturba-
449 tions, particularly in the tibialis muscle ($r = 0.68$, $p = 0.002$). These findings suggest an altered
450 structure–function relationship, where reduced WM integrity in the PPN-balance/locomotor
451 network may underlie delayed postural responses. This is consistent with evidence from human
452 and animal studies indicating that automatic postural responses are pre-selected by basal gan-
453 glia–cortical loops and released via brainstem circuits (Peterson et al., 2016). Collectively, this
454 reinforces the view that brainstem dysfunction contributes to balance control impairments in
455 PwMS.

456 *3.4. Supratentorial Regions Involvement*

457 Recent findings indicate that cortical thickness and lesion volume in specific supratentorial ar-
458 eas adversely affect balance performance in PwMS. In particular, motor cortex, atrophy espe-
459 cially in the precentral and paracentral gyri, has been found to be associated with impairment
460 in 360° turning performance, including turn duration, peak velocity, and turn angle (Swanson
461 & Fling, 2023). Furthermore, lesion volumes involving the cortex, frontal lobes, temporal lobes,
462 and parietal opercula in PwMS have been shown to delay postural responses and compromise
463 standing balance, especially under challenging sensory conditions that require integration of
464 incongruent proprioceptive and visual feedback (Doty et al., 2018).

465 Physiologically, lesions in these areas impair sensory integration and higher-order cognitive
466 functions, which are crucial for balance control and interfere with large-scale neural networks
467 responsible for multisensory input processing (Doty et al., 2018). Furthermore, lesions in these
468 areas can impair the neural circuits responsible for shaping postural responses, ultimately lead-
469 ing to delayed responses (Bolton, 2015; Jacobs & Horak, 2007).

470 A more detailed understanding of the relationship between cortical lesions and postural insta-
471 bility in PwMS necessitates an understanding of the cortical role in balance control. Below, we
472 summarize key insights from Jacobs and Horak (2007), who described the cortical contributions
473 to postural control.

474 Historically, automatic postural responses were thought to be primarily mediated by subcortical
475 structures, including the brainstem and spinal circuits, with minimal involvement from the
476 cerebral cortex. This belief was based on early studies demonstrating that animals with midbrain
477 transections retained many automatic reflexes that assist in correcting and maintaining posture.

478 However, more recent behavioral and empirical studies have revised this perspective, support-
479 ing the role of cortex in shaping postural responses, particularly in complex situations. Behav-
480 ioral studies have suggested that the cerebral cortex plays a key role in regulating posture by
481 integrating high-order cognitive functions, such as memory and attention, and by mediating
482 several cognitive-motor processes that can influence postural responses. These processes in-
483 clude: 1) changes in initial conditions such as stance width, support surface, and emotional state,
484 2) changes in attention and cognitive load when performing simultaneous tasks such as dual
485 task activities, 3) intention to react in specific strategy, and 4) learning and alteration of postural
486 responses strategies based on previous experiences. This conceptual framework is supported by
487 empirical evidence demonstrating associations between cognitive impairments and balance def-
488 icits.

489 On the other hand, empirical findings from human and animal studies have demonstrated that
490 individuals with intact brainstem function but cortical lesions exhibit abnormal postural re-
491 sponses to external perturbations. Moreover, empirical studies suggest that postural responses

492 are more context-specific and adaptable than spinal reflexes and require the activation of coor-
493 dinated muscle synergies throughout the body. While the initial phase of postural responses can
494 be mediated by spinal and brainstem circuits, cortical structures increasingly contribute during
495 the later phases, specifically when the initial phases of postural responses need refinement or
496 when compensatory stepping or reaching are needed to restore balance.

497 Beyond its direct role in shaping reactive responses, the cerebral cortex also modulates antici-
498 patory postural adjustments by priming brainstem circuits through loops involving the cerebel-
499 lum and basal ganglia. The cerebellum adapts the coordination and magnitude of responses
500 based on prior experience, while the basal ganglia loop preselects and enhances the response
501 according to the current situation.

502 Neuroanatomically, the cerebral cortex encompasses several sensory and motor areas that are
503 essential for maintaining balance, especially in response to external perturbations. Evidence
504 from studies investigating the impact of cerebral lesions on postural control elucidated these
505 areas. The insula has been found to be involved in the perception of the visual vertical. The
506 Thalamus, insula, and superior parietal cortex have been found to be involved in perceived
507 gravitational vertical. The Temporal-parietal junction has been found to be involved in multi-
508 sensory integration, and its lesion lead to impaired balance control on unstable surfaces (Jacobs
509 & Horak, 2007). The parietotemporal cortex has been found to be involved in multisensory
510 integration that contributes to the construction of a three-dimensional body schema essential for
511 maintaining postural verticality and self-consciousness. The prefrontal cortex has been found
512 to be involved in planning goal-oriented behaviors. The supplementary eye field and frontal eye
513 fields contribute to postural orientation and gaze alignment (Takakusaki et al., 2024). The cortex
514 and thalamus are involved in integrating sensory inputs for postural tasks. A distributed cortical
515 network encompassing the prefrontal cortex, supplementary motor area (SMA), and temporal-

516 parietal cortex are involved in integrating somatosensory and vestibular inputs to process infor-
517 mation concerned with self-motion and counteract balance loss.

518 Additionally, other findings based on electroencephalogram (EEG) studies demonstrate that in
519 response to postural perturbations, a small positive potential is detected over the primary sen-
520 sory cortex 40-50 ms after the perturbation, indicating its role in processing sensory signals. A
521 larger negative potential, observed 100-200 ms after unpredictable perturbations only is de-
522 tected over frontocentral regions, suggesting the involvement of cingulate cortex and the SMA,
523 probably in conjunction with the cerebellum, to generate an "error signal" that compares actual
524 versus expected sensory information concerning postural status. This finding highlights the sig-
525 nificance of these cortical areas in adjusting postural control in response to unexpected pertur-
526 bations.

527 Also, neurophysiological studies involving humans and animals have underscored the critical
528 role of the primary motor cortex in the late-phase of feet-in-place automatic postural responses
529 and in generating compensatory stepping responses to external perturbations. Also, these stud-
530 ies highlight the involvement of the supplementary motor cortex and primary sensory-motor
531 cortex in preparation for responses to external perturbations (Jacobs & Horak, 2007) (Table 1).
532 For a more detailed understanding of the neuroanatomical and neurophysiological mechanisms
533 underlying gait and postural control, we recommend a review by Takakusaki et al., (2024).

534 ***3.5. Interrupted Connection Between Distant Central Nervous System (CNS) Regions***

535 Numerous studies have demonstrated the detrimental impact of damage to the white matter
536 tracts on balance control in PwMS. Such structural damage can impair standing balance, even
537 under relatively stable conditions like standing on a firm surface with eyes open (Prosperini et
538 al., 2013; Tona et al., 2018). By disrupting the connections between different areas of the CNS

539 involved in controlling balance (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021; Prosperini et al., 2013), white
540 matter tract damage affects the central integration of various types of information, including
541 sensory, motor, and cognitive inputs necessary for balance control (Prosperini et al., 2013; Tona
542 et al., 2018). This ultimately results in balance dysfunction, manifested as increased postural
543 sway, particularly under challenging sensory conditions, such as standing on unstable surfaces.

544 Notably, Tona et al., 2018 demonstrated that reduced functional connectivity between the den-
545 tate nucleus and left caudate nucleus was associated with impaired standing balance perfor-
546 mance in PwMS, likely due to disrupted integration of sensorimotor and cognitive inputs (Tona
547 et al., 2018). Specifically, they reported a significant inverse correlation between functional
548 connectivity in these regions and center of pressure (COP) path displacement, indicating that
549 lower connectivity was linked to greater postural instability.

550 Functionally, the cerebellum, which plays a critical role in multisensory integration (Odem,
551 Richmond & Fling, 2021), is involved in both motor and non-motor functions through its den-
552 tate nucleus (Martinu & Monchi, 2013; Tommasin et al., 2022; Sbardella et al., 2017; Tona et
553 al., 2018). In contrast, the caudate nucleus contributes to cognitive and emotional aspects of
554 movement, through its connection with the prefrontal cortex (Tona et al., 2018). The intercon-
555 nection between the basal ganglia and cerebellum (Bostan et al., 2010; Hoshi et al., 2005;
556 Martinu & Monchi, 2013; Tommasin et al., 2022; Tona et al., 2018) allows for the integration
557 of both motor and non-motor information required for movement and balance control
558 (Tommasin et al., 2022). Consequently, functional disconnection between these subcortical
559 structures in PwMS impedes this integration, resulting in measurable postural deficits, as evi-
560 denced by increased postural sway in assessments using stabilometer.

561 ***3.6. Instability is a Multifactorial Event***

562 Recent research has provided a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms
563 underlying balance dysfunction in PwMS, indicating that such dysfunction likely arises from
564 multisystem involvement rather than impairment of a single neural system (Arpan et al., 2020;
565 Prosperini et al., 2014). The relative contribution of each system appears to depend on the
566 availability of sensory inputs under varying sensory conditions (Capone et al., 2019; Prosperini
567 et al., 2014; Prosperini & Castelli, 2018). This perspective was supported by evidence from
568 Prosperini et al. (Prosperini et al., 2014), who demonstrated that both spinal cord and cerebellar
569 dysfunctions contribute to balance dysfunction in PwMS. However, the relative contribution of
570 each system to this impairment varies depending on the available sensory conditions for balance
571 control. In the presence of all sensory inputs, the primary causes of balance dysfunction are
572 cerebellar atrophy and demyelination of the middle cerebellar peduncles. However, in the
573 absence of visual input, brainstem demyelination and spinal cord atrophy contribute to balance
574 dysfunction (Prosperini et al., 2014). These findings highlight the complexity of balance
575 control, which depends on the integrated function of distributed neural circuits that dynamically
576 adapt to various sensory conditions.

577 (Figure 3)

578 **4. Discussion**

579 The aim of this review was to provide a detailed comprehensive understanding of the neuroan-
580 atomical correlates involved in balance dysfunction in PwMS and the impact of their corre-
581 sponding functional impairments on different types of balance control systems, such as static
582 and dynamic balance, under different sensory conditions. This was achieved by reviewing pre-
583 vious studies that correlated neuroimaging (i.e., MRI) and/or neurophysiological test (i.e.,
584 SSEP) findings of various CNS regions with balance measures in PwMS. The results indicate

585 that, from an anatomical perspective, balance dysfunction in PwMS can arise from the involve-
586 ment of different CNS regions (i.e., cerebrum, cerebellum, brainstem, and spinal cord) and
587 functional circuits and connections (i.e., dentate-caudate nuclei functional connectivity). Fur-
588 thermore, balance dysfunction is likely to arise from multisystem involvement rather than just
589 one (Arpan et al., 2020; Prosperini et al., 2014). The relative contribution of each system to this
590 problem can vary among patients or depending on the available sensory inputs under different
591 clinical and environmental conditions (Capone et al., 2019; Prosperini & Castelli, 2018). How-
592 ever, from a functional perspective, balance dysfunction can result from impairments in sensory
593 integration and reweighting processes, impairments in central integration, and delayed postural
594 responses. Previous studies have identified these impairments as contributing factors to balance
595 dysfunction in PwMS. Specifically, research has shown that delayed postural responses in
596 PwMS affect both static (Huisinga et al., 2014) and dynamic balance (Huisinga et al., 2014;
597 Peebles et al., 2018). Moreover, findings have demonstrated that lesions in different CNS re-
598 gions involved in sensory integration can affect balance control under changing sensory condi-
599 tions (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021; Doty et al., 2018; Gera, Fling & Horak, 2020). Effective
600 postural control relies on the accurate integration of sensory inputs from the visual, vestibular,
601 and somatosensory systems (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021; Fling et al., 2014; Gera, Fling &
602 Horak, 2020; Prosperini et al., 2011), as well as the capacity to dynamically reweight these
603 inputs when sensory conditions change (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021). Consequently, a
604 deficient integration process can alter postural responses, compromise balance control, and in-
605 crease the risk of falls (Prosperini et al., 2011).

606 On the other hand, as this review primarily aimed to bridge existing gaps in the literature re-
607 garding the mechanisms underlying balance dysfunction in people with multiple sclerosis

608 (PwMS), by providing an in-depth analysis of the neuroanatomical regions involved and eluci-
609 dating how impairments in these regions affect different types of balance control systems. Ac-
610 cordingly, we found that:

611 ***In a static stance on a fixed support surface with the eyes open***, postural instability and balance
612 dysfunction in PwMS result from the involvement of the ascending spinal cord pathways, spe-
613 cifically DCML; descending spinal cord pathways; SCP; ICP; somatosensory cerebellar lob-
614 ules; brainstem, and disconnection between distant postural related areas. The dysfunction of
615 the DCML and ICP affect the transmission and integration of proprioceptive inputs, which are
616 crucial for balance control in this condition. However, the interrupted connection between dif-
617 ferent postural-related regions affects the central integration of various types of input necessary
618 for postural control (Odem, Richmond & Fling, 2021).

619 ***In a static stance on a fixed support surface with the eyes closed***, postural instability and bal-
620 ance dysfunction in PwMS result from the involvement of the ascending spinal cord pathways,
621 specifically DCML; descending spinal cord pathways; inferior cerebellar peduncles; soma-
622 tosensory cerebellar lobules; and brainstem. In this condition, the reliance on vestibular and
623 proprioceptive information for balance control increases (Prosperini et al., 2014; Gera, Fling &
624 Horak, 2020). Consequently, dysfunction in the spinal cord, ICP, as well as brainstem that carry
625 and/or integrate this information affect their transmission and integration, ultimately compro-
626 mising balance.

627 ***When standing on a compliant support surface with the eyes closed***, balance dysfunction is
628 attributed to the involvement of the ICP. However, when ***standing on a compliant support***
629 ***surface with the eyes open***, balance dysfunction results from the involvement of the MCP.
630 Balance control in these conditions relies on vestibular and visual information, respectively.

631 The ICP transmits vestibular information to the cerebellum, whereas the MCP conveys visual
632 information. As a result, impairments in the microstructural integrity of these peduncles, can
633 affect the sensory integration of their corresponding information, ultimately affecting vestibular-
634 lar- and visual- based balance control respectively.

635 *In dynamic conditions*, balance dysfunction can be attributed to the involvement of the DCML
636 and cerebellum. The slowed conduction of somatosensory signals carried by the DCML leads
637 to inaccurate sensory feedback, impaired inter-joint limb coordination, and delayed postural
638 responses, ultimately reducing the ability to adapt and navigate in dynamic environments. How-
639 ever, cerebellar dysfunction disrupts essential mechanisms involved in dynamic balance con-
640 trol, such as feed forward and feedback mechanisms.

641 *Delayed postural responses* following unexpected perturbations are attributed to lesions in the
642 spinal cord, brainstem, and cerebral cortex. These CNS areas play an important role in initiating,
643 shaping, and controlling postural responses in response to unexpected perturbations (Jacobs &
644 Horak, 2007). Subsequently, impairments in these regions have the potential to significantly
645 impact postural responses (Table 2).

646 Finally, it is worth mentioning that in addition to the aforementioned factors, other co-existing
647 impairments can also contribute to balance dysfunction in PwMS, such as cognitive status (Red-
648 licka et al., 2021) and spasticity (Sosnoff, Shin & Motl, 2010).

649 **Clinical Implications:**

650 **I. Assessment:**

651 **1- Comprehensive Assessment of Balance Impairments in PwMS:**

652 Balance control is a complex motor skill that demands the dynamic interaction of multiple phys-
653 iological systems, including sensory, motor, and cognitive systems, to maintain postural stabil-
654 ity. In PwMS, these systems are often impaired, leading to deficits in both static and dynamic
655 balance (Brincks et al., 2023; Wallin et al., 2024). These deficits manifest as impairments in
656 static stance, delayed postural responses to unpredictable displacements, slowed and diminished
657 movement toward the limits of stability (LOS) (Aruin et al., 2015; Cameron & Lord, 2010;
658 Cattaneo, Jonsdottir, & Coote, 2014; Forsberg et al., 2016; Ganesan et al., 2015), and impair-
659 ments in sensory integration and reweighting process (Doty et al., 2018; Gera et al., 2020; Odom
660 et al., 2021).

661 In clinical practice, identifying these impairments requires systematic and comprehensive as-
662 sessment using various diagnostic tools to precisely quantify performance across various do-
663 mains of the postural control system. Such assessments enhance diagnostic accuracy, facilitate
664 the identification of specific deficits, and ultimately support the development of targeted inter-
665 vention strategies tailored to individual patient needs (Horak et al., 2009; Pollock et al., 2000).

666 To guide clinical practice, the subsequent sections outline key assessment methodologies that
667 enable systematic and thorough evaluation of balance performance, facilitating the identifica-
668 tion of impairments across multiple domains of postural control in PwMS.

669 These methodologies include (1) quantification of static stance under varying sensory condi-
670 tions, (2) assessment of sensory integration and reweighting processes, (3) quantification of
671 reactive balance, and (4) evaluation of limits of stability (LOS).

672 **1.1.Static Stance under Varying Sensory Conditions and Sensory Integration and Re-**
673 **weighting Process:**

674 Effective balance control relies on several critical mechanisms. One of these mechanisms is the
675 ability of the central nervous system to integrate and reweight sensory inputs from the visual,
676 vestibular, and somatosensory systems to maintain postural stability (Calafiore et al., 2021; Cyr
677 et al., 2019). PwMS often exhibit increased postural sway during static stance and impairments
678 in sensory integration and reweighting process, contributing to balance dysfunction (Cameron
679 & Lord, 2010; Odom et al., 2021).

680 To objectively assess these deficits, tests such as the Sensory Organization Test (SOT) of Com-
681 puterized Dynamic Posturography or Clinical Test of Sensory Interaction on Balance (CSTIB)
682 are recommended. These assessments quantify static stance under varying or conflicting sen-
683 sory conditions (Cohen et al., 1993; Oliveira et al., 2011; Shim et al., 2018), thereby detect-
684 ing overreliance on specific sensory inputs and deficits in sensory reweighting process
685 (Oliveira et al., 2011; Shim et al., 2018).

686 **1.2 Reactive Balance:**

687 While the SOT and CTSIB are effective in evaluating static balance under varying sensory
688 conditions, they do not comprehensively assess other critical domains of balance control, such
689 as reactive balance responses. Alternatively, instrumented approaches introducing unpredicta-
690 ble perturbations such as dynamic force platforms demonstrated by Cameron et al., (2008) and
691 Huisinga et al., (2014) studies or the Motor Control Test (MCT) of Computerized Dynamic
692 Posturography (Vanicek et al., 2013) are required. These methods offer objective measures of
693 a person's ability to restore stability following unpredicted disturbances.

694 However, similar to SOT and CTSIB, these perturbation-based methods cannot provide com-
695 prehensive assessment for other balance impairments such as those related to the limits of sta-
696 bility. Consequently, other instrumental measures are necessary to evaluate such impairments
697 comprehensively.

698 **1.3 Limits of Stability:**

699 Typically, limits of stability are quantified using a stabilometer (Juras et al., 2008) or comput-
700 erized dynamic posturography (Ganesan et al., 2015), by instructing patients to move as swiftly
701 and as far as possible in specified directions. Empirical evidence demonstrates that PwMS ex-
702 hibit significant impairments in LOS performance, characterized by both reduced movement
703 velocity and decreased maximal displacement compared to healthy controls (Cameron & Lord,
704 2010). While the current review does not specifically examine the neuroanatomical correlates
705 of LOS capacity, its primary objective is to provide a comprehensive overview of balance im-
706 pairments in PwMS. Consequently, it became imperative to include both assessment method-
707 ologies and evidence-based intervention approaches that target LOS deficits.

708 **2- Subjective Evaluation Methods:**

709 Although instrumented assessment methods offer an objective and comprehensive evaluation
710 of balance control domains, their clinical application is predominantly confined to research-
711 oriented hospitals and specialized centers (Parrington et al., 2020). In routine clinical practice,
712 the implementation of such objective evaluations is limited by the scarcity of these instrumental
713 tools, which are costly and require specialized expertise. Consequently, subjective clinical
714 scales remain the primary means for assessing balance. In this context, it is advisable to utilize
715 scales such as the Mini Balance Evaluation Systems Test (Mini-BESTest), which can assess

716 key balance domains, including reactive postural control, adaptive responses, and dynamic sta-
717 bility during ambulation. This multidimensional evaluation provides comprehensive insights
718 into balance performance, thereby enhancing both the accuracy and practical utility of balance
719 assessments in real-world clinical settings (Wallin et al., 2024).

720 **II. Rehabilitation:**

721 **Optimal Balance Rehabilitation Regimen:**

722 Balance dysfunction is one of the most disabling symptoms experienced by PwMS (Prosperini
723 et al., 2013, 2014), It adversely affects domains of postural control (e.g. motor, sensory, cogni-
724 tive) throughout the disease course. Due to its significant impact on mobility, risk of falls, and
725 quality of life (Mazumder et al., 2014; Prosperini et al., 2014), identifying effective interven-
726 tions that target these impairments is crucial. Although numerous empirical studies have inves-
727 tigated the efficacy of various balance rehabilitation strategies, the existing literature lacks de-
728 finitive guidance on specific balance interventions to be incorporated into rehabilitation. This
729 ambiguity presents a significant challenge in clinical practice, where such information is critical
730 for designing effective and individualized training interventions for multiple sclerosis patients
731 (Brincks et al., 2023).

732 To address this gap, we propose that no single structured balance rehabilitation program will be
733 optimal for all patients due to the heterogeneity and variability of symptoms among patients.
734 Conceptually, interventions that effectively address specific balance impairments do not neces-
735 sarily result in a generalized improvement across other impairments, indicating the need for
736 diverse rehabilitation techniques to effectively address distinct balance impairments (Blasco et
737 al., 2023; Cattaneo et al., 2014; Dunsky, Zeev, & Netz, 2017; Hrysomallis, McLaughlin &
738 Goodman, 2006; Paillard et al., 2004). Here, it becomes imperative to conduct a systematic and

739 thorough assessment to identify the impairments experienced by each patient and propose suit-
740 able corresponding interventions accordingly (French et al., 2020).

741 Such interventions include:

- 742 • Exercises that challenge the extent of the body leaning toward the limits of stability to ef-
743 fectively address the limited capacities to reach these limits (Willaert et al., 2020). One
744 approach to achieve this is through weight-shifting exercises (Gouglidis et al., 2011) that
745 challenge the body toward the LOS (Willaert et al., 2020). Beyond traditional exercises in
746 routine clinical practice, emerging technologies such as exergames can offer a training ap-
747 proach that precisely challenges the extent of body leaning for each patient. Such approach
748 was illustrated by Ibrahim et al. 2024 (Ibrahim et al., 2024), who introduced an adaptive
749 exergame that enables the selection of the minimal degree of body leaning required for game
750 interaction. This allows for progressive increases in the required extent of body leaning,
751 thereby providing a controlled and scalable challenge to LOS.
- 752 • Exercises involving sensory integration training to address impaired static stance under var-
753 ying sensory conditions and impairments in sensory integration and reweighting processes.
754 This type of exercise has demonstrated superior results compared to similar exercises per-
755 formed without sensory variation or conventional methods (Cattaneo, Jonsdottir & Regola,
756 2014; Gandolfi et al., 2015).
- 757 • Exercises involving perturbation-based balance training and high-speed exercises tailored
758 to an individual's capabilities to address delayed postural responses to unpredictable pertur-
759 bations. Both types of exercise have demonstrated efficacy in addressing this impairment in
760 clinical trials. Specifically, perturbation-based balance training has been shown to be an
761 effective method for enhancing reactive balance responses, yielding superior outcomes

762 compared with conventional balance training interventions (Monjezi et al., 2023). High-
763 speed exercises, such as those integrated into exergames, can significantly reduce reaction
764 times (RT) for responding to external stimuli, thereby enhancing the ability to recover from
765 sudden balance disturbances and reduce the risk of falls (Anders et al., 2020; Callesen et al.,
766 2020).

767 • Exercises incorporating dual-task activities such as naming words within a category while
768 walking backward (a task with additional cognitive demand) or catching a ball while leaning
769 (a task with additional motor demand) are required to address impairments in the cognitive
770 domain of postural control (Brincks et al., 2023).

771 • Exercises involving task-oriented training for addressing impairments associated with func-
772 tional tasks, such as transition from sitting to standing or context-specific task. To improve
773 stability associated with specific motor tasks (Khallaf, 2020; Teasell et al., 2008).

774 • Other targeted exercises to address co-impairments, such as spasticity (Sosnoff et al., 2010),
775 which may be associated with postural instability stability.

776 By incorporating such diverse interventions into balance rehabilitation programs, these pro-
777 grams can be more effective in targeting a wide range of balance impairments, thereby enhanc-
778 ing the overall therapeutic outcomes.

779 **5. Conclusions**

780 The aim of this review was to offer novel insights into the neurophysiological mechanisms
781 underlying balance dysfunction in PwMS, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive un-
782 derstanding of this dysfunction and offering clinicians a theoretical framework for developing
783 targeted therapeutic interventions. The findings indicate that, from an anatomical perspective,

784 balance dysfunction originates from multisystem involvement rather than one (Arpan et al.,
785 2020; Prosperini et al., 2014). The relative contribution of each system can vary among indi-
786 viduals and depends on the availability of sensory inputs under different clinical and environ-
787 mental conditions. However, from a functional perspective, postural balance instability is likely
788 to arise from impairments in sensory integration and reweighting process, delayed postural re-
789 sponses, and impairments in central integration. Given this complexity, a systematic and indi-
790 vidualized assessment is essential to identify specific impairments in each patient and tailor
791 corresponding interventions. Such interventions include sensory integration training, perturba-
792 tion-based balance training, and task-oriented approaches. By targeting distinct deficits, reha-
793 bilitation programs can be optimized to enhance therapeutic outcomes.

794 **6. Clarification**

795 The neuroanatomical regions implicated in balance dysfunction under particular conditions, as
796 discussed in this review, were derived from studies conducted to date. Consequently, these re-
797 gions are not definitive, and future studies could broaden our understanding of the involvement
798 of additional CNS regions in balance dysfunction under various conditions.

799 **7. Limitations**

800 The discussion in this review focuses on dynamic balance in general, without specifically ad-
801 dressing reactive and anticipatory balance. This was due to the stated aim of the included stud-
802 ies, which was to investigate the association between lesions in various CNS regions and bal-
803 ance problems in patients with multiple sclerosis (PwMS). However, it is preferable to use sep-
804 arate methodologies to assess the reactive and anticipatory balance. This would provide a
805 clearer understanding of the impact of each CNS region on each type of balance, and advance

806 the development of targeted training regimens based on the affected area and its corresponding
807 functional impairment.

808 **8. Future Recommendations**

809 For future research, we recommend investigating the relationship between balance dysfunction
810 and the involvement of additional CNS regions that are not discussed in this review. Addition-
811 ally, it would be beneficial to explore the connection between the same regions mentioned in
812 this review, but under different sensory conditions than those previously evaluated. These in-
813 vestigations may reveal new associations that can advance our understanding of this field and
814 ultimately facilitate the development of more targeted rehabilitation approaches.

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818 Diab.

819 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Figure 1, Flow chart of records identified, screened, and included in the review.

Figure 2, Schematic representation of the dorsal column medial lemniscus pathway (adapted from Purves D., Neuroscience, 2nd edition (2001)).

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1181 **Figure 3**, Illustrates the central nervous system regions contributing to postural and balance

1182 dysfunction in patients with multiple sclerosis. (A) supratentorial region (cerebrum), (B)

1183 white matter tracts, (C) brainstem, (D) spinal cord, and (E) cerebellum (figure developed in

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BioRender.com).

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1197 **Table 1**, Summary of cortical areas involved in postural control and their respective func-
 1198 tions.

Cortical area	Role in postural control
Insula	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception of the visual vertical. • Perceived gravitational vertical.
Thalamus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived gravitational vertical. • Integrating sensory inputs for postural tasks.
Superior parietal cortex	Perceived gravitational vertical.
Temporal-parietal junction	Multisensory integration.
Parietotemporal cortex	Multisensory integration that contributes to the construction of a three-dimensional body schema essential for maintaining postural verticality and self-consciousness.
Prefrontal cortex	Planning goal-oriented behaviors.
Supplementary eye field	Postural orientation and gaze alignment.
Frontal eye field	Postural orientation and gaze alignment.
Cortex	Integrating sensory inputs for postural tasks.

Distributed cortical network encompassing the prefrontal cortex, supplementary motor area, and temporal-parietal cortex	Integrating somatosensory and vestibular inputs to process information concerned with self-motion and counteract balance loss.
Primary sensory cortex	Processing sensory information in response to perturbation.
Cingulate cortex and supplementary motor area, probably in conjunction with the cerebellum	Generate an "error signal" that compares actual versus expected sensory information concerning postural status in response to unexpected perturbations.
Primary motor cortex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Late-phase of feet-in-place automatic postural responses. • Generating compensatory stepping responses to external perturbations.
Supplementary motor cortex and primary sensory-motor cortex	Preparation for responses to external perturbations.

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1205 **Table 2**, Summary of the various central nervous system regions that contribute to postural
 1206 instability and balance dysfunction under different sensory conditions available for postural
 1207 and balance control.

Condition	Involved areas
Static balance with open eyes	Dorsal column medial lemniscus pathway, spinal cord descending tracts (further studies needed to identify specifically which tracts), inferior cerebellar peduncles, superior cerebellar peduncle, cerebellar lobule I-V, brainstem, disconnection between distant postural related areas.
Static balance with closed eyes	Dorsal column medial lemniscus pathway, spinal cord descending tracts (further studies needed to identify specifically which tracts), inferior cerebellar peduncles, cerebellar lobules I-V, brainstem, and specific cortical regions.
Standing on compliant surface with closed eye condition	Inferior cerebellar peduncles.
Standing on compliant surface with open eye condition	Middle cerebellar peduncles.
Dynamic condition	Dorsal column medial lemniscus pathway (future studies needed to identify the involvement of spinal cord descending tracts) and cerebellum.
Delayed postural responses following unexpected perturbations	Spinal cord pathways (afferent and efferent), brainstem, and certain supratentorial regions.

1208 N.B: lesion volumes to certain supratentorial regions can result in balance dysfunction, espe-
1209 cially in challenging sensory conditions that require the integration of incongruent propriocep-
1210 tive and visual feedback

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